

GuidelinesClaudinha

Consumer Law (EN)

11/05/2024, São Paulo

v. 3.0

VERSION HISTORY

Version	Validity	Changes	Responsible
V0	09/2021 - 02/2022	- Initial version.	Ananda, Felipe, Guilherme, Igor, Jéssica, Prof. Jaime Sichman, Prof. Juliano Maranhão, Prof. Roberto Pfeiffer, Raphael.
V1	02/2022 - 06/2022	- Review of V0; - Exclusion of the tags indicated in “History of Deleted Tags”; - Addition of tags in the First PPD Block, specifying the holder's rights; - Aggregation of tags in the Second PPD Block; - Changes to the Third PPD Block.	Felipe, Igor, Jessica, Raphael
V2	06/2022	- Formatting changes; - Creation of the topic “History of Deleted Tags”; - Update of the summary.	Igor, Jessica
V3	07/2022	- Deletion of the 'Controller Contact' tag to join with the 'Controller ID' tag - Deletion of the 'Treatment Hypotheses' tag - Unification of the tags “generic expressions” and “non-specific quantifiers” - Deletion of the tags “Substantial treatment information” and “Concision” - Deletion of the 'personal data processing' tag	Felipe, Jessica.

SUMMARY

1. Tagging instructions for Consumer Law	3
1.1.Types of mapped clauses	3
1.2.Degrees of abusiveness	5
1.3.Technical details	13

1. Tagging instructions for Consumer Law

The purpose of this section of the guidelines is: i) to present the idea of tagging Consumer Contracts to the Claudinha Project team and open it for comments; ii) provide instructions on how to undertake this task.

1.1.Types of mapped clauses

Clause type	What is it about?	Symbol
Consumer Law		
Jurisdiction	Where will the eventual legal proceeding be judged? (in which court?)	<j>
Limitation of Liability	What damages does the supplier say they will not be responsible for?	<ltl>
Unilateral Termination of the Contract	Under what conditions can the supplier unilaterally terminate the contract?	<ter>
Unilateral Modification of the Contract	Under what conditions can the supplier unilaterally modify the terms of the contract?	<ch>
Compulsory Arbitration	Is it mandatory for the dispute to be presented to an arbitration court before it can be submitted to the judiciary?	<a>
Transfer of Liability to Third Parties	Does the supplier transfer its responsibility to third parties?	<tpt>
Contract by Using	Is the consumer bound by the terms of service simply by using the service?	<use>
Content Removal	Under what conditions can the service provider/supplier remove user content?	<cr>
Responsibility for possible legal costs	Does the supplier oblige the consumer to pay compensation if they break the contract without, however, stipulating it to their own disadvantage?	<ci>

Limitation on the right to return the product	Does the supplier limit the consumer's right to return the product in any way?	<return>
Deleted Tags		
Choice of Law	Defines the legislation of which country will be applied to the case	Not applicable under Brazilian law
Privacy Included	The consent form also guarantees consent regarding the privacy policy	No practical example found in our law
Clause that presupposes the existence between the parties of consent or effective negotiation regarding the clauses and terms of the contract	Whether there is consent or effective negotiation by the parties regarding all terms of the contract	<neg>

1.2.Degrees of abusiveness

We understand an unfair clause as a contractual clause that was not individually negotiated which causes a significant imbalance in the rights and obligations of the parties arising from the contract, to the detriment of the consumer.

As noted, this is a very general principle. For purposes of applicability to the Claudinha Project, the annex below contains a list of clauses that, if identified in the Consumer Contracts analyzed, present signs of potential abuse (eg reversal of the burden of proof). For classification purposes, the instruction below was based on various sources - mainly court decisions - which, however, do not provide answers to all questions.

In this sense, we proposed the following three-fold gradation: 1, for fair treatment, in which the clause meets all legal requirements and does not contain abusive content; 2, for potentially unfair; and 3, for unfair..

For example:

- <j1> Clause containing displacement of jurisdiction that is fair </j1>
- <cr2> Clause containing potentially unfair conditions for excluding content. </cr2>
- <ter3> Clause with unilateral termination of the contract that is clearly unfair. </ter3>

We also discussed how necessary the presence of a certain clause is for its analysis. This degree of necessity is, therefore, defined as “YES” when the presence is, in fact, necessary or “NO”, when abusiveness is detected by the absence of mention of any contractual term or provision.

Clause type	Need for express presence in the contract	Degree of abusiveness	Conditions	Example	Observations/Justification
Jurisdiction	Yes	1	When the jurisdiction clause exists, but directs it to the consumer's place of residence.	<j1> It is hereby established that any dispute, controversy, or claim arising out of or related to this contract shall be resolved in the jurisdiction of the consumer's place of residence, in accordance with applicable law. </j1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	<j2> (...) </j2>	
		3	When the jurisdiction clause exists, but it directs to a location other than where the consumer resides	<j3>All claims arising out of or relating to these terms or the Services will be litigated exclusively in the federal or state courts of Santa Clara County, California, USA, and you and Google consent to personal jurisdiction in those courts.</j3>	

Limitation of Liability	Yes	1	It provides that the supplier is responsible for all damages caused, as well as defects of any nature, etc.	<lt;1>The supplier shall be fully responsible for all damages caused by their actions, as well as for any defects of any nature that may occur in the products or services provided. This responsibility includes both material and moral damages, directly or indirectly related to the subject of this contract.</1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	<lt;2>(…)</2>	
		3	It provides that the supplier will not be responsible for damages caused, as well as defects of any nature, etc.	<lt;3>The supplier shall not be responsible for any damages caused by their actions, nor for any defects of any nature that may occur in the products or services provided. This exemption includes both material and moral damages, directly or indirectly related to the subject of this contract.</3>	In the Claudette project, the researchers understood that there was no level 3 of abusiveness in this case, but only level 2. Here, the option for level 3 was due to the express provision of art. 51 I of the CDC

Unilateral Termination of the Contract	Yes	1	When there is a clause that allows both the supplier and the consumer to unilaterally terminate the contract	<ter1>Both the supplier and the consumer shall have the right to unilaterally terminate this contract at any time. Such termination shall be effective upon written notice to the other party, without the need for further justification or compensation.<ter1>	
		2	Not applicable	<ter2>(…)<ter2>	
		3	When there is a clause that allows the supplier to terminate the contract unilaterally, without allowing the consumer to do so.	<ter3>The supplier shall have the right to unilaterally terminate this contract at any time without allowing the consumer the same right. Such termination shall be effective upon written notice to the consumer, without the need for further justification or compensation.<ter3>	
Unilateral Modification of the Contract	Yes	1	Not applicable	<ch1>(…)<ch1>	
		2	Not applicable	<ch2>(…)<ch2>	

		3	When there is a clause allowing the supplier, unilaterally, to change the content or quality of the contract	<ch3>The supplier is authorized to unilaterally alter the content or quality of this contract at their discretion. These modifications will become effective upon providing written notice to the consumer, who agrees to accept the changes without requiring additional approva<ch3>	
Compulsory Arbitration	Yes	1	Not applicable	<a1>(…)<a1>	
		2	Not applicable	<a2>(…)<a2>	
		3	When a clause determines the mandatory use of arbitration to resolve disputes	<a3>Any disputes that arise from or are related to this contract must be resolved through binding arbitration, following the rules and procedures set by [Arbitration Organization]. The parties agree that arbitration will be the sole method for resolving any such disputes, thereby foregoing court litigation.<a3>	

Transfer of Liability to Third Parties	Yes	1	Not applicable	<tpt1>(…)<tpt1>	
		2	Not applicable	<tpt2>(…)<tpt2>	
		3	<p>When there is a clause that transfers or assigns EXCLUSIVE liability (solidarity is not a problem) for any defects in the provision of services to third parties. This is the case of an internet operator that transfers Liability for any problems in installing services to a third-party company.</p> <p>OR</p> <p><i>Market place</i> which transfers all Liability to the product provider</p>	<tpt3>All liability for any defects or issues related to the services provided will be fully transferred to third parties.<tpt3>	
<i>Contract by using</i>	Yes	1	Not applicable	<use1>(…)<use1>	
		2	Not applicable	<use2>(…)<use2>	

		3	Any clause that presumes consent, whether through use of the service or using the opt-out logic (offenses to information duties, articles 6,30 and 31 of the Brazilian Consumer Law Code)	<use3>By continuing to use the platform after the effective date of these terms, the user consents to all terms and conditions herein, including any updates or modifications made by the provider. This includes but is not limited to, changes in service fees or privacy policies.<use3>	
Content Removal	Yes	1	When it provides clear criteria and reasons for the procedure used in cases of eventual content exclusion.	<cr1>The platform reserves the right to remove content that violates our community guidelines, infringes intellectual property rights, or poses legal risks. Content removal will be accompanied by a notification detailing the specific reasons and criteria for the action taken. Users may appeal the removal decision by submitting a formal request within 7 days of notification<cr1>	
		2	When the supplier stipulates generic criteria for removing content	<cr2>The marketplace may remove listings or content that are deemed offensive,	

				misleading, or violate our terms of service. This includes but is not limited to, prohibited items, fraudulent activities, or inappropriate content. The decision to remove content will be based on general criteria outlined in our community standards<cr2>	
		3	When there is no explanation, criteria or motivation for removing content	<cr3>The service provider reserves the right to remove any content that violates our terms of use or legal obligations. Removal decisions are at the sole discretion of the provider and may occur without prior notice or explanation to the user.<cr3>	
Responsibility for possible legal costs	Yes	1	Not applicable	<ci1>(...)<ci1>	
		2	Not applicable	<ci2>(...)<ci2>	
		3	Allocation of all legal costs on the consumer. Example: clause that imposes on the consumer the obligation to	<ci3>In the event of legal action initiated by either party to enforce obligations under this contract, the consumer	

			pay costs and legal fees in the event of an action being filed	agrees to bear all costs associated with legal fees, court charges, and attorney fees incurred by the supplier<ci3>	
Any limitation on the right to return the product	Yes	1	Not applicable	<cen1>(…)<cen1>	
		2	Not applicable.	<cen2>(…)<cen2>	
		3	Any clause that limits the right to return the product in accordance with the bases of art. 49 of the CDC. Example: prohibition of returns, imposition of costs on returns, restriction or conditioning of returns to another obligation, restriction of the return period, etc.	<cen3>Both parties expressly acknowledge and agree that all terms and conditions of this contract have been mutually negotiated and agreed upon. Each party confirms having had the opportunity to review, discuss, and understand the terms before entering into this agreement. Any amendments or modifications to this contract shall require the mutual consent of both parties in writing.<cen3>	

Tip: If you are not sure about the level of illegality of each clause, mark it with the “?” instead of a number. Please notify this in the group and update our query sheet

1.3. Technical details

1. The *.xml format will be used to save the files.
2. Please, when tagging, select the entire sentence, example: `<use2>By using the Services you agree to be bound by these Terms.</use2>`
3. Please fill the table in the file titled “The tagged terms” with EVERY sentence you tagged, according to the template and example. From that table we will derive the grammar for the automatic soft.